

Interviews: current state review

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

We wanted to explore the current state of user centred approaches experience within the EDS and beyond. To do this, we formally interviewed 18 individuals who work in environmental, digital/data domains or user centred approaches specifically. We also had many informal verbal and written discussions with individuals from a range of research domains and organisation types.

We've summarised our findings in this document and have included:

- A synthesis of common themes used to frame this report.
- A list of individuals (in digital research infrastructure roles) who are interested in domain specific good practice for user centred approaches.
- Links to more detailed notes for highlighted interviews.
- Some opportunities for future collaborations.

Methodology

We used our existing network to reach out to individuals and organisations to have conversations with us. We reached out to over 25 different organisations, some of whom replied and were willing to be interviewed. The email details we shared with the interviewees are below. The optimum time for an interview was 1 hour.

Context for why we want to talk to interviewees:

We've set up a group of experts [across the EDS](#) interested in user centred approaches. We're trying to share good practice and guidance to help others who design, maintain and develop data services for environmental science. We've been developing [a beta toolkit here](#).

We're reaching out to individuals and organisations (within environmental data or more broadly across digital research infrastructures), to understand their experience in this area and understand if this toolkit and/or a community of practice is something useful to expand in the future.

Questions:

- What past experience do you/your team have in the user centred design/co-creation spaces?
 - Environmental science?
 - Digital Research Infrastructure?
- Key things you're working on now or in the future (in terms of user focused / co-creation). Are we trying to solve the same problem?
- What do you think are the biggest challenges related to user centred approaches?
 - For us it is funding (we need an evidence bank of why this work is useful to support future proposals - do you have any resources/papers?)
- Do you think there is value in continuing discussions? What would you want that to look like?
- Is there anyone else you think we should talk to? Any other resources we could look at?

Synthesis

We had conversations with 18 individuals from 12 different organisations. Some of the key conversations are summarised below. We reached out to a diverse range of individuals and organisations, see Table 1 for a summary - some resulting in interviews, informal discussions or email chains.

NetDRIVE

The Network for sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure Vision and Expertise (NetDRIVE) has been set up to provide a forum for managers, software engineers, academics and others to come together to build a common vision for a sustainable future and to incite a transition to sustainable working practices in the Digital Research Infrastructure communities.

We spoke to one of the co-leads of NetDRIVE who received 6 months of funding to write the proposal for NetDRIVE in a collaborative way, including a diverse range of users, DRI providers and community leaders.

Met Office

We spoke to the User Experience lead at the Met Office. The team has grown from 4 to 20 people in the last few years as the Met Office has shifted to be more user focused. They have a background in user research and innovation.

We also spoke to an applied scientist at the Met Office who works with customers (e.g. private sector, government) to make climate science delivered at the Met Office relevant to them. They have over 15 years of experience at the Met Office working with stakeholders and users.

Met Office International Climate Services

We spoke to the Science Manager of the International Climate Services at the Met Office. He has a background in meteorology and climate science, but has moved to work engaging with people to co-produce climate services. He has a joint position at the Met Office and University of Bristol with a focus on how climate science and services can be made more useful to wider international context.

His role also involves understanding decision-making contexts so that services provided are useful for climate change adaptations and climate risks. He is particularly interested in African climate services and completed a post-doc in Cape Town. He leads the Weather and Climate Science for Service Partnership (WCSSP) South Africa project.

Research Data Alliance

We spoke to a research scientist based in Indiana University at the Luddy School of Informatics, Computing, and Engineering. She has a background in social sciences and has transitioned to data services and practices.

Her research focuses on emerging technologies, digital media, and data practices. She works on interdisciplinary projects that promote open science, data preservation, and data sharing. Additionally, she applies her language and regional expertise to analyze digital narratives.

FAIR data accelerator

The FAIR Data Accelerator project seeks to understand hidden social and cultural barriers to data sharing and how to address them at scale. It could transform the way research is undertaken, how outputs are shared, and hone ways of working and workplace structures.

Brighton User Centred Design Laboratory, University of Brighton

We spoke to a Principal Lecturer in Human Centred AI and Interaction at the School of Architecture, Technology and Engineering, University of Brighton. She leads and manages the [Brighton User Centred Design Laboratory](#) which provides Research and Consultancy in the areas of Human Centred AI, User Experience Design (UX), Product Development, and UX testing and Evaluation.

DAFNI DINI

WE spoke to the Data Engineering Theme Lead and DAFNI Programme Lead and the Project Delivery Manager who are both based within Scientific Computing at the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC). They work with teams who are developing and maintaining digital research infrastructures or working within data/digital domains.

The DINI project examines what is needed to deliver data and good research with impact for government, industry and the public at large. The DAFNI DINI project focuses on the requirements and impact of supporting sharing and analysis of data across National Infrastructure systems, with a focus on energy, water and transport, and the related natural, built and social and economic environment.

Health Data UK

Health Data UK is the national institute for health data science. Their mission is to unite the UK's health data to enable discoveries that improve people's lives. We spoke to the user experience team of two. Both were relatively new to their roles at HDR, with previous UX design experience from the private sector and experience in public engagement and medical communication.

AutSPACE project

We spoke to two individuals (formerly) from the Alan Turing institute about their [AutSPACEs project](#). This was a 5 year project, where people with autism can share stories about their senses with other users and allies, to help make the world more comfortable and inclusive. All documentation is [publicly available on Github](#).

Table 1: a summary of organisations we contacted for an interview. The table indicates their research domain, where they are based, and the job role of individuals we reached out to. Formal interview notes have been included where possible.

Organisation	Organisation type	Domain	Country	Job role	Further information
Research Data Alliance	Community driven	Digital preservation and research data management	International	Research Scientist	Interview notes
NetDRIVE	Academic	Environmental science Interdisciplinary	UK	Project lead	Interview notes
Met Office	Executive agency	Environmental science	UK	Science Manager, International Climate Services User-experience lead, and Applied scientist	Interview notes Interview notes
University of Brighton	Academic	Economic, social, behavioural and human data science Computer science - AI, data science	UK	Principal Lecturer in Human Centred AI and Interaction	Interview notes
DAFNI DINI	Research infrastructure	Computer science - software, data science	UK	DAFNI Programme Lead, and Project Delivery	Interview notes

		Engineering and physical sciences		Manager	
Health Data UK	Government	Health	UK	User experience team	Interview notes
FAIR Data Accelerator	Academic	Digital preservation and research data management Economic, social, behavioural and human data science	UK	Project lead, social science researcher	Informal discussion so no notes available
IPCC Interactive Atlas	International community	Environmental science	International	Computer science PhD student	Informal discussion so no notes available
Sustainable Software Institute	Academic	Computer science - software	UK	Project Manager	Informal discussion so no notes available
Alan Turing institute	Independent charity	Computer science - AI, data science	UK	-	Informal discussion so no notes available
Catapult	Industry	Engineering and physical sciences	UK	-	Informal discussion so no notes available
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam	Academic	Digital preservation and research data management	International	-	Ran out of time to organise interview
National Film and Sound Archive	Government	Digital preservation and research data management	International	-	No response to email
US geological survey	Government	Environmental research	International	-	Yes - limited time so no notes
NOAA	Government	Environmental research	International	-	No response to email
Surfers against sewage	Community driven /	Environmental research, Health	UK	-	No response to email

	Independent charity				
Environment Agency	executive non-departmental public body	Environmental research	UK	-	No response to email
Brunel University London	Academic	Economic, social, behavioural and human data science Environmental research	UK	-	No response to email
UK Government departments specialising in user centred approaches	Government	-	UK	-	Ran out of time to organise interview, email exchange instead
Sustainable DRI project	Academic	Computer science - AI, Data Science Environmental research	UK	-	Ran out of time to organise interview
ECMWF	Independent intergovernmental organisation	Environmental research Computer science - AI, Data Science Digital preservation and research data management	International	-	Ran out of time to organise interview
Earth Observation DataHub (EODH)	Research infrastructure, industry	Environmental research Computer science - AI, Data Science Digital preservation and research data management	UK	-	Ran out of time to organise interview

Common themes

We spoke to people from a wide range of backgrounds with varied levels of user centred approaches implemented within their team structures.

For example, the Met Office has a centralised User Centred Design team which has rapidly grown in recent years. Each person in this team is dedicated to a single project and their working time and task management comes from within the project team funding them. They also have external suppliers that can provide people part time to work on smaller projects.

We also spoke to the smaller UX team at HDR who are assigned across multiple projects dependent on funding and resources available.

Our interview with an expert in user centred design and leader of the [Brighton User Centred Design Laboratory](#) focused on her research around the emerging discipline of [Human centered AI](#). This discipline is intent on creating AI systems that amplify and augment rather than displace human abilities. We discussed how human centred AI could be used to benefit all aspects of user centred approaches. e.g. how AI could be used (alongside design thinking principles) to define personas.

Finally we spoke to a number of people implementing user centred design in their work in less structured ways.

A common theme across approaches was the importance of considering outcomes over outputs when designing a service. This considers the impact the service has or decisions made following on from its use, not just the whether it functions.

Community of practice

- To bring people together who are doing work in areas such as social science and user centred design.
- Some groups we spoke to have existing internal communities of practice for user-centred design (e.g. Met Office). It was a common theme that people were interested in both developing a common community of practice across disciplines and learning from these existing ones.

Mindset shifts/upskilling teams

- Education within teams surrounding user centred approaches - not just asking users what they want but discovering what they need
- Using an 'elevator pitch' - one slide to summarise what they want to achieve
- Broadly two types of services were discussed that are created at the Met Office with different approaches:
 - Data driven services - where there is an urgency to get data out there - landscape of people who can do the tailoring e.g. large tech companies
 - User engagement services - dealing with particular groups who require more co-production to understand what they need.

Ways of engaging users

- NetDRIVE conducted community workshops to gather feedback on their approach - this encouraged a shift from problem focus to people focus
- They also employed a diverse range of champions for shorter amounts of time (e.g. 1 day a week) to reach larger group of people from within their institutions, and to go where networks exist already
- Keeping an eye on existing community discussions
- We spoke to a research scientist who highlighted the importance of being embedded within project teams from the start for her work - observing pain points to tailor services to address these. Furthermore, this can support UX designers embedded in teams to have necessary expertise to communicate with the same language.
- We talked to the FAIR data accelerator lead about the importance of finding a hook to encourage users to engage in development of services and focus on problems important to the user
- Though they don't have systematic user centred design focussed approach, the DAFNI team regularly show prototypes to users and get feedback as standard practice. HDR spoke of the mind-set shift needed for this within their team to overcome the reluctance to show incomplete work to users when domain science is built on trust, and shifting to trust by transparency and engagement.
- To gather evidence for the DAFNI DINI project, sandpit projects, champions and workshops were used to engage with the community:
 - Sandpit projects - a mechanism for getting together a range of experts who wouldn't usually work together, creating a proposal and successful bids receive funding to do the work
 - Champions - a closed funded opportunity as a mechanism to target community experts
 - Workshops - to speak with academia, government and industry to understand the different opportunities and barriers in data sharing
- The Met Office applied science team have internal public weather service representation for external users (e.g. forecasters, aircraft, etc.) who constantly inform development of new services/data visualisations/products based on their needs

Lessons learnt

A mindset shift from outputs to outcomes. Considering the impact the service has or decisions made following on from its use, not just the whether it functions.

- Shift from problem focus 'here's a problem we'd like to solve' to people focus
- Changing the measurable outcomes of a project from the service itself to its impact: What will the users get out of it? What future impacts will the service have? What decisions might be made following on from its use?
- Create an elevator pitch - what do we want to achieve summarised on a single slide?

Reaching users: use diverse and creative methods

- Sandpit projects - a mechanism for getting together a range of experts who wouldn't usually work together, creating a proposal and successful bids receive funding to do the work
- Champions - a closed funded opportunity as a mechanism to target community experts
- Workshops - to speak with academia, government and industry to understand the different opportunities and barriers in data sharing
- Clarity about who users are - ensuring the focus is on users and not just what the customer wants and distinguishing these two groups.

Assessing users' needs can help with deciding how much user engagement to perform in a project - is the priority getting the service out there or building relationships with the user community? This can depend on the project. E.g.

- Data driven services - urgency to the data/service out there - landscape of people who can do the tailoring e.g. big tech companies
- User engagement services - dealing with particular groups who need more co-production to understand what they need

This requires a clear understanding of what user centred design is - it is not asking users what they want but discovering what they need.

Furthermore, having internal representation for external users can inform the development of new services/data visualisations/products based on their needs.

Involving users from the start. Implementing a user-focus from the start of the project, gathering feedback through community workshops, and being a part of team meetings from the start to assess needs will help define the direction of the project.

- To address tight timescales, it is important to have people on board from the start who will engage and are familiar with the goals of the project
- Keeping an eye on existing community discussions

Creating scalable services from the outset. Time and funding is needed for scaling services from the outset, but this allows services developed to reach a wider audience and can reduce repetition of work and tools.

- An example from the Met Office: the local authority climate service - this started from work closely with one local authority but as other groups heard about it's successes there was a need to expand the service, now scaled up to be applied to any UK local authority
- 'Begin with the end in mind'

Building trust

- Allowing users to feel represented in the process
- Being open - e.g. making proposal public, having NERC presence at meetings shows interest from the top
- Being flexible - allowing research to lead the direction of the work

- Involves overcoming the reluctance to show incomplete work to users when domain science is built on trust, and shifting from trust by 'perfection' of delivered services to trust by transparency and engagement.
- Engaging with social scientists - evaluating where you've got trust is more difficult than e.g. when you have consensus. Social scientists can help with evaluating this.
- Helps to have domain specific experience for engagement - ensuring you are speaking the same language as your users

Finding a hook to draw communities in and encourage user engagement, showing how your service is relevant to them. The hook is different for different communities and should be understood further for specific communities related to the Environmental Data Service.

Diversity of ideas

- Involve social science and expertise to bring in new concepts (that are often not new to social scientists, but new to us as DRI/data people).
- Resisting going down one track and keeping an open mind
- Allowing contradictions and conflicts of ideas that come naturally from working with diverse group
- To manage the diverse range of views and openness of the work, focus on understanding how you will get measurable impact from the work, with target of immediate progress

User centred design is domain agnostic. We can learn from other disciplines.

Conflict: embedded UX individual or work spread across networks?

- When developing a user centred service, spreading work across multiple people to reach a greater network of users allows a diversity of input however having few, specific UX people assigned to the project from the start allows them to be embedded in the team to build trust and learn team mindsets and challenges.
- This highlights the range in approaches to UX design - we must choose approaches that can work for our team structures and resources

Challenges

Many common challenges were shared across the interviews. These came under the following broad themes: understanding and engaging users, flexibility and openness in co-creation, changing patterns and mindsets, lack of resources, time restraints, funding structures and working with diversity and across silos.

Understanding and engaging the user

- Encouraging users to engage in the design process has been a common challenge across the interviews. Often users aren't funded to trial services and share their experiences and so don't have the interest or capacity to contribute.

- Finding a hook to draw people in has been highlighted as a challenge, particularly for engaging domain scientists. This means research often relies on champions to give feedback, which can lead to biases and lack of full representation from the user base.
- The challenge of defining the difference between customers and users was also highlighted as something often missed in user centred design, particularly when these overlap.
- It was discussed that often as teams we can articulate what we want to do better than who our users are and what they need. Shifting to a more user-focused approach requires a change in mindset and current working patterns.
- For the Met Office, an additional challenge was the presence of competitors - other providers can offer similar services, this makes user centred services very important

Flexibility and openness of co-creation

- User-focused design and co-production requires flexibility to adjust outcomes based on user needs.
- Many interviewees gave examples of challenges this can pose for funding and timescales, as well as putting strain on the individuals working on the project.
- It is not always clear what direction a co-produced project will go in, and it was found that best practices for co-production on resources and time don't always align with specific situations.
- An example was given where engaging with users created a shift in focus of the project from the data provision to the people and problems it is trying to address. Though this allowed trust to be built up with the community, the outcomes were more difficult to measure and involved less data provision than anticipated. This poses questions about how user centred services are developed:
 - How do you select which products should be co-produced? Based on impact?
 - Do you consciously not engage in problem space where the data/service may be relevant and just focus on making it accessible and usable?

Changing patterns and mindsets

- Implementing mindset shifts on a wide scale across departments is a challenge.
- Previously, when working out and applying for funding it is already decided what is going to be built. Co-production requires a more agile approach and the ability to stop, shift focus, and be flexible with outcomes, but teams need to be able to structure and fund this.
- Fear of sharing incomplete work with users - a lot of scientific work is based on trust and there is a reluctance to share unfinished work with users (particularly highlighted by the UX team at Health Data UK).
 - Shifting this mindset to trust built by transparency and making users feel included in the process is needed.
- Often software design ends up being back-end first and is not always designed with users' needs as a priority. Where there is no systematic approach to user centred design, a change in focus is needed.
- The current output focus leads to too many tools doing the same thing that don't get maintained properly, as they are not built from outside in - 'disjointed legacy systems and services'

- Shifting views on behavioural change - acknowledging that change involves us not others and keeping this idea present without it being an anxiety.
- Using the right language. There is lots of jargon in this field of work - user centred design, co-creation, co-production, participatory research, user experience... etc. Finding common terminology that everyone understands to describe the methods of working together with people to create a service.

Lack of resources

- Lack of resources dedicated to user centred design was a common challenge and teams don't always have resources to invest in user research.
- Limited staff resources due to retention issues and recruitment freezes and small UX teams were common.
- Solutions included outsourcing work to partners, upskilling colleagues in user focused design and making use of opportunities to share staff resources amongst teams.
- Expectation management - users don't fully appreciate the work required in the background for services that look simple on the surface

Time restraints

- Challenge to get good engagement and actionable feedback in a limited time from a range of diverse backgrounds
- The vastness of evidence collected that needs synthesising takes time.
- Delivery focus rather than user focus puts more emphasis on deadlines. This makes teams unable/reluctant to involve many users on short time scales
- Short time scale for funding (and compressed further due to delays)
 - Not enough time to gather user feedback
 - No real solution, often exacerbated alongside staffing challenges.
- High turnover of designers on projects - need to spend time unpicking the work from the start, slow approval process for change

Funding

- Many interviewees expressed how lack of funding puts limits on the amount of user centred design possible and can be a barrier to collaboration. In particular, getting funding support from domain science was a challenge.
- It was also expressed that funding structures create challenges against the open and agile work approach needed for user centred design. When funding calls are often focused on outputs, this can limit the flexibility for the project to progress in different directions that are unclear from the start.
- Many suggested the short funding as a challenge for flexibility however it was also suggested that short funding scales could work if the funding is more open to route changes, pivots and discovery. More iterative funding, for a phase rather than based on specific outputs, would allow more flexibility for starting with a broader goal or change in mind and allowing research to lead the direction of the work. Funding for a short validating stage was also suggested for e.g. testing how broad the user base for a service may become to allow planning for scalability of the service from the start.

Working with diversity and across silos

- Deficit in contributions from early career people - less likely to speak up in meetings
- Everyone has their own ideas and problems which can be very different (especially gathered from a diverse audience) - it is a challenge to synthesize these and get from brainstorming to coalescing to recommendations.
 - Managing contradictions and conflicts of ideas is both a challenge and a positive aspect of working with diverse group - creating room for different views from people starting from different backgrounds
- Different disciplines have varied norms in the way they use and share data, different concerns about how data will be perceived and interpreted by others, and different contexts to the impact of data on professional identities and career pathways. different research domains have different cultures related to data sharing.
- There is often a stigma associated with reaching out to social sciences, interdisciplinary collaboration is not necessarily built into work patterns at institutions. There is a wealth of knowledge that can be gained from social scientists about user centred design.
- Additional challenges with international work:
 - Institutional politics, agendas
 - Diversity - e.g. reaching out to the most vulnerable communities - only the less vulnerable have the means to communicate/are plugged into institutions
- Research in different disciplines can be very siloed. This poses challenges for co-production across disciplines where people are used to working with different tools, particularly when these use proprietary software or have access restrictions. Examples highlighted where silos often exist include between social scientists and data scientists, and data managers and scientists.

Collaboration opportunities and future recommendations

FAIR data accelerator

- We are both creating practical resources to help a particular community. Both sets of resources could be useful across domains, with nuances related to the domain's existing culture.
- We are both looking at ways of bringing in social science and expertise to bring in new concepts (not new to social scientists, new to us as DRI/data people).
- It was valuable to share experiences with stepping outside our usual research domains (environmental/astronomy, digital research infrastructures) and working with social science researchers/techniques. These techniques are not new (to social scientists) but they are to many of us who work in digital research infrastructure. It would be valuable to explore this further.
- The work we are doing is complementary. It could be combined into a wider holistic toolkit that could be used by any digital research infrastructure. E.g. a toolkit with themes such as; data sharing, user centred approaches, training and skills, accessibility.
- We liked the idea of community of practices across digital research infrastructure, to bring people together who are doing work in areas such as social science and user centred design.

University of Brighton

- Work with the Brighton User Centred Design Lab to support for user experience developments
- Human centred AI domain - co-creation (humans and AI), how AI can support user experience in the environmental science domain
- Equality, diversity and inclusion - user perspectives, accessibility of data (for users and AI)
- Education and training (for our staff)

Potential mechanisms for collaboration:

- Project partner
- Pitch an idea for MSc student projects - Oct 2025
- Host a placement student - Oct 2025

DAFNI

- Future project across teams about implementing user centred design practices in our teams
- Sharing good practice

HDR UX team

- Keen to be involved, beneficial to develop community of practice and share across domains
- Broadening toolkit to wider audience, domain specific case studies

Some future recommendations include:

- Embed key themes and challenges into EDS roadmap and strategy
- Explore collaboration opportunities further